

Research methodology

An efficient inoculation method for rice blast

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Inoculation of pathogen isolates to the host is a fundamental tool for studying genetic aspects of both the pathogen and the host. Various inoculation methods have been developed for plant pathology studies. The spray method has most often been used in studies on rice blast because it is convenient and reproducible results are obtained. This method has limitations, however, because it may kill the plant. In molecular genetic studies, F₂ plants usually must be maintained for DNA extraction and for production of F₃ seeds. To avoid killing susceptible individuals, phenotypic segregation data are often collected by progeny testing, causing a lag in completing the analysis. We report here an efficient blast inoculation method for a F₂ mapping population.

To demonstrate this method, two F₂ populations developed from a cross of CO 39 with Tetep were used. Two hundred thirty-five seeds were germinated for population 1, and 132 seeds for population 2. Twenty seeds each of CO 39 and Tetep were grown together for inoculation as checks. Seedlings (one per pot) were grown in 5-cm-diam pots in a greenhouse for 21 d before inoculation. Isolate V85094, which was compatible with CO39 but incompatible with Tetep, was selected for this study. Inoculum was prepared from cultures grown on rice polish agar and prune agar. The concentration of the inoculum was adjusted to 1×10^5 spores/ml in 0.02% Tween 20 solution.

Seedlings were laid down on a bench. The youngest leaf that was at least half expanded was selected for inoculation. A 5-cm portion in the middle of the leaf was marked with a pen, and this portion was pricked in five sites with a pin. To wet the leaf surface, the entire leaf was brushed with water containing 0.02% Tween 20 using a soft artist's brush. The leaf was then wiped with a paper towel until dry. A brush dipped in inoculum was applied to the treated leaf. The inoculated seedlings were transferred to a dew chamber and incubated for 24 h at 26 °C, and then kept in a mist room for 6 d before disease evaluation.

Disease was evaluated using a 0-4 scale where 0 = no visual lesions, 1 = tiny brown pinpoint lesions, 2 = roundish, brown, nonsporulating lesions, 3 = roundish, small, weakly or nonsporulating lesions with dark margins, 3+ = large sporulating lesions with dark margins, without the typical spindle shape, and 4 = large spindle-shaped sporulating lesions with or without dark margins. Disease reactions with scores of 0-3 were classified as resistant, while those with scores 3+ and 4 were considered susceptible.

All of the plants of the susceptible parent CO 39 showed infection, while none of the plants of the resistant parent Tetep showed lesions (see table). Consistent reactions of the wounded and intact leaf segments were observed. The segregation of population 1 was significantly different from 3:1 (resistant to susceptible) at both 1 and 5% levels, with an excess of susceptible reactions. The segregation ratio of population 2 was significantly different from the 3:1 at 5%

but not at 1%. The distorted segregation ratio could be because of the many nongerminated seeds in both populations. Lesions on noninoculated portions of leaves were rarely observed, and no seedlings were killed due to inoculation. After disease evaluation, infected leaf parts were removed, and the seedlings were transplanted into plastic pails for production of F₃ seed. Seedling growth was not affected.

Although the method described here seems tedious compared with spray inoculation, two persons finished inoculating two populations in only one afternoon. By using the brushing method of inoculation, we could collect segregation data, extract DNA, and harvest abundant F₃ seeds for all plant genotypes in the population in the same growing season. ■

A computer-aided, alternating current-based feeding monitor for detecting activities of plant sap-sucking rice insects

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A computer-aided feeding monitor has been developed to study the activities of plant sap-sucking rice insects. The feeding monitor consists of an alternating current (AC) probe for detecting changes in conductivity between the insect and the plant, an analogue-to-digital converter (data translation DT2801 A-D card) fitted to an IBM-compatible personal computer (PC), and logging software to collect the data (BioSoft Oscilloscope) (Fig. 1).

The waveform patterns are characterized by their frequency and amplitude characteristics. Software is used to view the logged waveforms, to add even markers (Markplot), to summarize statistically the marked events (Markstat), to calculate the frequency spectra of the waveform, and to store characteristic waveform patterns. Graphical output can be directed to a color graphics metafile

Disease reactions of two F₂ populations and their parents to isolate V85094 of *P. grisea* using brushing inoculation method in a greenhouse.

	Total seeds (no.)	Total seedlings (no.)	Disease reaction		χ^2 value for 3:1 ^a
			Resistant	Susceptible	
F ₂ population 1	283	235	147	88	19.417**
F ₂ population 2	164	134	89	45	5.264*
CO 39	20	20	0	20	
Tetep	20	20	20	0	

*, ** = significant difference at 5 and 1% significance level, respectively.

1. Computer-aided, AC-based feeding monitor. A = chart recorder, B = AC-based feeding monitor, C = rice plant with "wired" insect, and D = computer.

(CGM) for importing into specialized graphics packages, such as Lotus Freelance, or to file in Hewlett Packard (HP) Graphics Language (HPGL) for HP plotters. The "current" screen may be dumped to an Epson FX80 printer.

By selecting a suitable data acquisition rate, the computer can be set to construct waveform patterns similar to a chart recorder. The advantages of using a computer over a traditional chart recorder include simplicity in marking and categorizing the different waveform patterns generated during long recording periods, automated statistical analysis,

convenient storage, recreation and comparison of waveform patterns, and capacity for detailed analysis of very minute feeding events.

The computer-aided feeding monitor may be used for a range of insect feeding-related experiments. For example, we studied the feeding behavior of rice green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant) on TN1 and IR62 for 3-h and 6-h periods. Typical waveforms were recorded on the chart recorder as well as on the PC while insects were not feeding, probing, and feeding. Waveforms were correlated with nonfeeding

and probing activities by observing the "wired" insect through a dissection microscope. Waveforms with specific feeding activity, such as phloem feeding and nonphloem feeding (xylem and mesophyll parenchyma), were correlated by the histological examination of salivary tracts in the leaf tissue as well as by testing the chemical nature of the honeydew produced. Five other types of waveforms were also recognized and categorized as miscellaneous waveforms, but these have yet to be correlated with specific activities (waveforms not shown). Measuring the time spent on these activities enables feeding-related activities to be quantified.

Twenty GLH were recorded for 3 h on TN1 and IR62 and then compared. Twelve GLH were also recorded for 6 h on TN1 and IR62 to see whether any marked differences exist in feeding behavior due to prolonged recordings. The different waveforms recorded on both the chart recorder and computer were classified into nonfeeding, probing, phloem feeding, nonphloem feeding, and miscellaneous waveforms as described above. Noticeable differences were apparent between the 3 h and 6 h recordings. The differences in time spent probing, phloem feeding, and nonphloem feeding on the varieties were more obvious during 6 h of recording rather than during 3 h (Fig. 2). ■

2. Average time on each feeding-related activity by 20 *N. virescens* on a susceptible rice variety (TN1) and a resistant rice variety (IR62) for 3 h and by 12 insects for 6 h.